

UnityGeoAR: A geolocation Augmented Reality package for Unity3D

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Abstract

Research interest in Augmented Reality (AR) has been steadily increasing in the past decades. However, while we see a wide range of publications implementing AR nowadays, it is often the case that the software is not included in the publication, leading to future research having to re-introduce similar custom AR solutions. We identify one such case, that of geolocated AR, which poses a deceptively complex issue, namely that of correctly aligning a virtual view with geo-referenced material around the user. We present here UnityGeoAR, a package for the widely used game engine Unity3D, that handles geolocation, reprojection, and AR view alignment through a minimal Application Programming Interface (API), in an effort to standardize geo-AR development and reduce development and implementation time for such a widely used aspect of AR.

Keywords: Augmented Reality, Geospatial, Unity3D

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Metadata

Nr.	Code metadata description	Please fill in this column
C1	Current code version	0.3.2
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/cheliotk/UnityGeoAR
C3	Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	none
C4	Legal Code License	GNU General Public License
C5	Code versioning system used	git
C6	Software code languages, tools, and services used	Unity3D, C#, DotSpatial.Projections, OpenElevation, OpenTopoData, Nominatim, OpenRouteService
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Unity 2021.3.19 or later, with ARFoundation 4.2.7 or later
C8	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/cheliotk/UnityGeoAR#readme
C9	Support email for questions	cheliotisk@mail.ntua.gr

Table 1: Code metadata (mandatory)

1. Motivation and significance

The field of Augmented Reality (AR) has received significant focus in the past decades, with many sectors applying such methodologies for their particular needs. In previous work [1] we have highlighted the inherent spatial nature of AR and its different aspects in terms of visualization size, scale, and methods of aligning the view between virtual and physical environment. One particular aspect of AR is *geospatial* applications, which deploy visualizations at *larger than human size*, presented at the *same scale*, using *geolocation* to align the virtual and physical views (following the classification system presented in [1]). While geospatial AR constitutes one of the earliest AR research applications [2], it is of particular interest here as the task of combining AR with geolocation is a deceptively complex issue.

1.1. Problem definition

Geospatial sciences offer a wealth of data and methods for accurately measuring locations on the Earth's surface. AR technology matches a virtual and a physical camera's movements so that virtual objects appear to be anchored to the user's immediate environment. Their combination appears fairly straightforward at first glance: Given a user's geolocation, to place geo-located points of interest so that they appear at their "correct" position around the user. However behind the scenes there is a number of processes that take place, which are not immediately straightforward.

More specifically, there are multiple spatial systems in existence at the same time, each with its own limitations, and all of them need to be in alignment for the user to see virtual objects accurately positioned around them. Essentially, four spatial reference systems need to be considered: Earth space, user space, virtual space, and avatar space.

27 *Earth space.* Refers to Earth, with locations defined as coordinate pairs in a
28 Coordinate Reference System (CRS), and with a true north heading, defined
29 as a compass pointing North.

30 *User space.* Refers to the user/device in the physical world. Its relevant
31 properties such as position and orientation are defined in Earth space context
32 (e.g. geo-location, compass heading). Properties may be changed by the user
33 interacting in physical space (e.g. moving around/rotating the device in their
34 hands).

35 *Virtual space.* Refers to software representation of 3D space. Most commonly
36 the virtual space is set up as an abstract three-dimensional Cartesian space
37 with the origin at (0,0,0), and a maximum distance threshold from the origin
38 on any axis¹. Virtual objects are always placed in relation to the origin.

39 *Avatar space.* Refers to the virtual camera that acts as an avatar of the
40 physical camera, and renders virtual objects onto a device's screen. The
41 virtual camera operates in virtual local space, and as such it is often initial-
42 ized with default values². Any subsequent movements and rotations of the
43 physical camera are copied to the virtual AR camera as offsets to its initial
44 position/rotation. Values may be overridden by a developer.

45 A geo-located AR app needs to perform multiple tasks within and across
46 these spatial systems: The geo-location of points of interest may have been
47 recorded in any of a number of CRS; The coordinate values most likely need

¹Due to floating-point precision errors and rendering distance, it is a common assumption that users will interact around the origin of the virtual space, e.g. Unity3D limits space at 100,000 units(meters)

²For example In Unity's AR package ARFoundation, the virtual camera is initialized at the virtual space origin, with its initial rotation on any axis set to 0.

48 to be converted to a format usable by the AR software; The physical camera's
49 geo-location and rotation in physical 3D space needs to be taken into account;
50 Elevations need to be accounted for so that objects are placed at the correct
51 heights; All of the above need to be fed into a single spatial system for the
52 virtual camera to detect and render.

53 Most of these tasks have been individually solved in their respective fields:
54 It is trivial for most cartographic libraries to reproject from any one CRS to
55 another on the fly nowadays; and AR technologies can continuously track a
56 camera's movements in space, place virtual objects around the user, and an-
57 chor them consistently through space regardless of camera movement. These
58 tasks have also been implemented in geolocated AR apps already [3, 4, 5].
59 However the geolocation/AR methodology and software is often not included
60 in publications, meaning that each team implements their own solution; Fur-
61 thermore, to our knowledge no tool exists that allows a streamlined combina-
62 tion of all these, so that a developer can provide a geolocation and accurately
63 position virtual elements around it given their geolocation, without needing
64 to also implement algorithms for all of the above tasks.

65 In response to this we present here UnityGeoAR, a library for Unity3D that
66 uses existing C# and .NET spatial libraries in combination with Unity's
67 ARFoundation package to accurately position geo-referenced objects around
68 the user's geo-location, obeying compass heading and elevation/height.

69 *1.2. Contribution*

70 The aim of this library is to streamline the development of geo-located AR ap-
71 plications. By bundling the reprojection and spatial calculations within the
72 library and providing a simple Application Programming Interface (API), the
73 library can do the heavy lifting and allow developers to focus on the features
74 relevant to their application. This library is expected to be especially bene-

75 ficial to researchers bringing their domain expertise into AR via Unity, but
76 are not necessarily experienced in Unity and .NET workflows: UnityGeoAR
77 handles the spatial reprojection and AR, allowing researchers to focus on
78 their research topic rather than debugging their application.

79 UnityGeoAR was initially developed as part of an AR navigation application
80 that the team at the Cartography Laboratory at NTUA are using for user
81 experiments (publications currently in writing). Early in the development
82 phase the core functionality's potential outside of the scope of the AR navi-
83 gation app was identified, and therefore the core AR-geopositioning logic has
84 been refactored into UnityGeoAR as standalone libraries, so that they may
85 be reused by the wider community.

86 *1.3. Experimental setting/Usage*

87 Researchers interested in implementing UnityGeoAR should download the
88 files provided in the linked repository and import them in their Unity project,
89 or download the whole repository (the repository is set up as a Unity project)
90 and open it in the Unity Editor. Either way enables users to make use
91 of UnityGeoAR's functionality; afterwards they are able to develop their
92 applications on top of UnityGeoAR.

93 *1.4. Related work/Dependencies*

94 UnityGeoAR is a collection of C# classes intended to be used in Unity3D
95 for AR application development. As such UnityGeoAR is a Unity-specific
96 library. Also, while not a technical dependency, ARFoundation (Unity's AR
97 toolkit) is heavily recommended.

98 Additionally UnityGeoAR depends on a number of external tools: It includes
99 DotSpatial³, a powerful GIS library written for .NET, to handle reprojec-

³<https://github.com/DotSpatial/DotSpatial>

100 tions between different CRS. Furthermore, UnityGeoAR relies on a number
101 of open-source and public web APIs for various purposes: openRoutingSer-
102 vice⁴ for routing/directions queries, openStreetMap's Nominatim⁵ API for
103 geocoding purposes, and public APIs for elevation data, with support for
104 two open-source elevation APIs: Open-Elevation⁶ and Open Topo Data⁷.
105 Finally, UnityGeoAR is intended for geo-located applications, and therefore
106 applications should be deployed to GPS-enabled devices, e.g. smartphones
107 with Location services enabled for the app. For dependency versions, please
108 refer to Table 1.

109 **2. Software description**

110 Given the multiple spatial reference systems discussed earlier, it becomes
111 evident that matching a real-world location and view to a virtual one in
112 Unity is a complex task. Therefore when using geolocated data in Unity it
113 is imperative to convert from any projection system's units to Unity's scene
114 units, in order to accurately place elements close to the origin.

115 UnityGeoAR handles this conversion in four steps, with an additional op-
116 tional step. First, each scene has two CRS attached to it: the source CRS, in
117 the format of the incoming data (e.g. EPSG:WGS84 as lat/long coordinate
118 pairs), and the destination CRS in meters, using a CRS that minimizes defor-
119 mations at the user's location (e.g. EPSG:27700 OSGB36/British National
120 Grid minimizes error in UK locations, while EPSG:2100 GGRS87/Greek
121 Grid minimizes error in Greek locations). These CRS do not have default

⁴<https://openrouteservice.org/>

⁵<https://nominatim.org/>

⁶<https://open-elevation.com/>

⁷<https://www.opentopodata.org/>

122 or inferred values, and should be set explicitly by the developer or provide a
123 method for users to set them.

124 Second, when a Unity scene is first initialized a `locationAtSceneStart` value
125 is attached to the particular scene, corresponding to the location/coordinate
126 pair of the device in the real world. This may be retrieved by the
127 device's GPS receiver. This location is reprojected from the source CRS
128 to the destination CRS, generating a `positionAtSceneStart`. Similarly, a
129 `compassHeadingAtSceneStart` is also attached to the scene, retrieved by the
130 device's compass. Optionally, the device's elevation is also recorded (assuming
131 user is outside at ground level), stored as `heightAtSceneStart`. These
132 values act as offsets to subsequent visualizations in the scene's lifetime.

133 Third, immediately after scene initial values are set, the virtual camera is
134 rotated around its vertical (yaw) axis by `compassHeadingAtSceneStart` degrees,
135 therefore matching the virtual camera's rotation to the real-world camera's
136 heading. This process establishes the overall camera rotation, and no
137 additional steps are required for this.

138 Fourth and final step, any point that needs to be visualized in scene space
139 is first reprojected from the scene's source CRS to the destination CRS, and
140 then offset by the `positionAtSceneStart` value. This new offset position is
141 used to place the object in the virtual space.

142 As an optional step, if the user has also requested elevation/height data, the
143 point's elevation is also queried. The returned elevation is then offset by
144 `heightAtSceneStart`, and the resulting height is set as the object's height
145 in scene.

146 The above steps ensure that the following conditions are true: All points
147 of interest are positioned in virtual space around the virtual space's origin
148 and within its distance thresholds, conforming to the virtual space's render-

149 ing limitations. The virtual space's orientation on the horizontal plane is
150 anchored to a real-world value so that virtual positive forward axis points
151 North with the other horizontal axis perpendicular to it, therefore rotation-
152 ally aligning the two spatial reference systems. And finally the virtual cam-
153 era's horizontal rotation is matched to the physical device's angle from North,
154 ensuring that the two cameras are at the same orientation relative to their
155 spatial reference systems' axes. These conditions ensure that any subsequent
156 visualization of geo-located objects can be accurately positioned in virtual
157 space as well.

158 *2.1. Software architecture*

159 UnityGeoAR is set up as a collection of standalone modules, each one devel-
160 oped as a self-contained Service. Furthermore, UnityGeoAR's Services are
161 built in layers, with some services developed as core generalized use-agnostic
162 modules, others as helper services combining multiple core modules for ease
163 of use, and finally services built specifically for navigation use. The full list
164 of UnityGeoAR Services is presented in Table 2.

165 Additionally an interface `ISceneController` is provided that defines the
166 various properties for holding scene data (such as position/compassHead-
167 ing/elevation atSceneStart). This interface should be implemented by a
168 `MonoBehaviour` in the scene, or the provided `ARSceneController` imple-
169 mentation may be used. Finally a `MonoBehaviour` called `LocationUpdater`
170 is provided that initiates and notifies other classes for device location up-
171 dates, which may be used as-is.

172 *2.2. Software functionalities*

173 Each service in UnityGeoAR is built as a .NET class, with a constructor and
174 minimal API.

Name	Type	Description
Reprojection	Core	Handles reprojection of coordinate pairs between ESRI projection systems. Implements DotSpatial
ElevationQuery	Core	Retrieves height data for a provided location. Implements elevation web APIs
LocationUpdates	Core	Retrieves geolocation and compass data from the current device's embedded sensors. Requires location data to be enabled
WorldToUnity	Helper	Combines ReprojectionService and ElevationQueryService, providing a single interface for converting a point from world space coordinates to Unity space position
Geocoder	Navigation	Handles geocoding (translating a human-readable description of a place to its coordinates). Implements openStreetMaps open-source geocoder Nominatim ⁸
Routing	Navigation	Navigation service. Handles routing between provided points. Implements the open-source openRouteService web API ⁹

Table 2: UnityGeoAR Services

Constructor	Public API
public ReprojectionService (int sourceProjectionEpsgCode, int destinationProjectionEpsgCode)	public Vector2 ReprojectPoint (double lat, double lng)
	public Vector2 ReprojectPointReverse (double lat, double lng)
	public Vector2[] ReprojectPoints (double[] lats, double[] lngs)
	public Vector2[] ReprojectPointsReverse (double[] lats, double[] lngs)
public ElevationQueryService ()	public async Task<OpenTopoDataResponse> MakeOpenTopoDataQuery (List<Vector2> locations, ElevationAPI elevationApi)
public LocationUpdatesService (float desiredAccuracyInMeters, float updateDistanceInMeters)	public bool InitializeService ()
	public bool IsInitialized ()
	public bool TryGetLatestCompassData (ref CompassData outCompassData)
	public CompassData GetLatestCompassData ()
	public bool TryGetLatestLocationData (ref LocationData outLocationData)
	public LocationData GetLatestLocationData ()
	public bool TryGetLatestLocationCompassData (ref LocationCompassData outLocationCompassData)
	public LocationCompassData GetLatestLocationCompassData ()

Table 3: Core Services

175 *2.2.1. Core Services*

176 The core services in UnityGeoAR handle the task of aligning the current
177 local view in Unity space to the user’s point of view in the real world. Two
178 of the services handle the conversion of coordinate pairs to Unity space
179 (**ReprojectionService** and **ElevationQueryService**), while another one
180 (**LocationUpdatesService**) handles location updates so the virtual scene
181 is aware of the user’s location and orientation in the real world. The con-
182 structors along with the exposed public API for each are presented in Table
183 3.

184 *2.2.2. Helper Services*

185 UnityGeoAR also provides a helper service called **WorldToUnityService**,
186 that contains instances of **ReprojectionService** and **ElevationQueryService**,

Constructor	Public API
<pre>public WorldToUnityService(ReprojectionService reprojectionService, ElevationQueryService elevationQueryService, Vector2 locationSourceLatLng, Dictionary<ElevationAPI, float> elevationsAtStart)</pre>	<pre>public async Task<Vector3> GetUnityPosFromCoords(Vector2 xyCoords, ElevationAPI elevationAPI)</pre>
	<pre>public async Task<List<Vector3>> GetUnityPosFromCoords(List<Vector2> xyCoords, ElevationAPI elevationAPI)</pre>

Table 4: Helper Services

Constructor	Public API
<pre>public GeocoderService(string geocoderApiBase)</pre>	<pre>public void MakeQuery(string searchTerm)</pre>
<pre>public RoutingService(string openRouteServiceApiKey, string directionsApiBase, string directionsProfile)</pre>	<pre>public event EventHandler<OpenRouteServiceResponse> onRouteReceived</pre>
	<pre>public void SetTargetLocation(Vector2 targetLatLng) public void StartQueryWithParameters(Vector2 startLatLng, Vector2 endLatLng)</pre>

Table 5: Navigation Services

187 and provides a single interface for converting a point from world coordinate
188 pair to local Unity space, including elevation (if requested). This service does
189 not introduce additional functionality compared to the two core services it
190 wraps around, and is only provided for ease of use. Its constructor and public
191 API are presented in Table 4.

192 2.2.3. Navigation Services

193 Due to its initial development as an AR navigation application, UnityGeoAR
194 also contains two services that are specifically tailored towards navigation
195 tasks. The two navigation services provide access to public web APIs for
196 geocoding and routing (**GeocoderService** and **RoutingService** respectively),
197 so that users may look for a place near them by name and calculate a walking
198 route to it from their current location. The constructors and APIs for each
199 navigation service are presented in Table 5.

200 **3. Illustrative examples**

201 In this section we present the usage of UnityGeoAR as part of an AR nav-
202 igation app. The AR navigation app implements a straightforward logic:
203 Given a route consisting of waypoints in world coordinate pairs, the route is
204 rendered via AR so that its waypoints are overlaid accurately over the ac-
205 tual positions in the real world. As the user moves in the real environment,
206 the visualized route is consistently anchored in space correctly, so that the
207 user can follow it by "walking along a line". An example of the AR Naviga-
208 tion app can be seen in the accompanying video in the online version of this
209 article.

210 *3.1. Acquiring route waypoints*

211 We implement two methods for acquiring the route waypoints: either by
212 using preset routes, or by using a combination of services to generate a route
213 during runtime. Both approaches result in an ordered list of waypoints from
214 origin to destination, with each waypoint expressed as a coordinate pair.
215 The resulting list of waypoints can then be fed into the route visualizer for
216 rendering.

217 *Preset routes.* For preset routes developers need to provide precalculated
218 routes, which may then be selected by the user during runtime. The routes
219 can be formatted as a simple text or .csv file, with one waypoint per line,
220 ordered from first to last, and with each waypoint provided as a (y,x) coor-
221 dinate pair. A sample preset route is presented in Table 6. Since the virtual
222 scene is set up with the user's current location as the origin, a selected preset
223 route's waypoints must be close to the user's location for it to be visible.

224 *Geocoder.* A second option for acquiring a route is for the user to search for
225 places around them, select a destination, and calculate a route to it. This

y	x
23.73537	37.99502
23.73534	37.99489
23.73531	37.99474
23.73529	37.99466
23.73525	37.99448
...	...

Table 6: Sample preset route format

226 approach utilizes the **Geocoder**, **LocationUpdates**, and **Routing Services**:
 227 The geocoder service looks for place names nearby matching a string term
 228 and returns a list of geocoder results, each containing a lat-long coordinate
 229 pair as metadata. After the user selects a result, its lat-long pair is stored as
 230 the destination, and the user's current lat-long (as obtained by the location
 231 updates service) is set as the origin. These are then passed to the routing
 232 service, which calculates a walk path from origin to destination, returning it
 233 as an ordered list of waypoints in lat-long format. An example of this flow
 234 is presented in Listing 1.

```

235 1 // Get destination location
236 2 var address = new Uri($"{geocoderApiBase}q={searchTerm}&format=geojson");
237 3 string responseData = await httpClient.GetAsync(address)
238 4     .Content.ReadAsStringAsync();
239 5 NominatimResponse geocodedResults = JsonConvert
240 6     .DeserializeObject<NominatimResponse>(responseData);
241 7 List<double> destination = geocodedResults.features[0]
242 8     .geometry.coordinates;
243 9 Vector2 destinationLatLong = new Vector2(destination[1], destination[0]);
244 0
245 1 // Get current location as origin

```

```

246.2 Vector2 originLatLng = locationUpdater
247.3     .lastLocationCompassData.location.toVector_2();
248.4
249.5 // Add listener to handle calculated route
250.6 routingService.onRouteReceived += RoutingService_onRouteReceived;
251.7
252.8 // Calculate path from origin to destination
253.9 routingService.StartQueryWithParameters(originLatLng, destinationLatLng);

```

Listing 1: Routing using geocoder

254 3.2. Route visualization

255 In order to visualize a route in AR, the source route waypoints need to first
256 be reprojected from world coordinates to local Unity space. Following that, a
257 route visualizer can generate graphics and 3D models and place them in the
258 Unity scene, at the correct positions. An example of the route visualization
259 flow is shown in Listing 2

```

260.1 OpenRouteServiceResponse response;
261.2 // Convert from OpenRouteService to list of Vector2 coordinate pairs
262.3 List<Vector2> waypointLatLngs = new List<Vector2>();
263.4 foreach (Feature feature in response.features) {
264.5     List<List<double>> coords = feature.geometry.coordinates;
265.6     foreach (List<double> coord in coords)
266.7         waypointLatLngs.Add(new Vector2(coord[0], coord[1]));
267.8 }
268.9
269.0 // Convert from lat-long pairs to Unity space
270.1 List<Vector3> waypointPositions = await sceneController
271.2     .WorldToUnityService
272.3     .GetUnityPosFromCoords(waypointLatLngs, ElevationAPI.NO_ELEVATION);
273.4
274.5 // Create a LineRenderer GameObject to hold all the waypoints

```

```

275.6 GameObject line = Instantiate(linePrefab);
276.7 LineRenderer lineRenderer = line.GetComponent<LineRenderer>();
277.8 lineRenderer.positionCount = waypointPositions.Count;
278.9
279.0 // Iterate over the waypoints
280.1 for (int i = 0; i < waypointPositions.Count; i++) {
281.2     // For each waypoint, set the corresponding index of the LineRenderer
282.3     lineRenderer.SetPosition(i, waypointPositions[i]);
283.4
284.5     // Instantiate an additional graphic for each waypoint
285.6     GameObject waypoint = Instantiate(waypointPrefab,
286.7         waypointPositions[i],
287.8         Quaternion.identity);
288.9 }

```

Listing 2: Route visualizer logic

289 4. Impact

290 The major impacts of UnityGeoAR are identified in three main categories:
291 its ease of use, its extensibility, and its fields of application.

292 4.1. Ease of use

293 UnityGeoAR provides tools that streamline the process of visualizing geo-
294 located elements via AR in Unity3D. Therefore developers already accus-
295 tomed with the Unity platform and C# will find a familiar interface that
296 handles the non-Unity cartographic tasks behind the scenes, allowing them
297 to focus on Unity-specific tasks such as visualization and overall app logic.
298 On the other hand researchers (and especially geospatial practitioners) not
299 familiar with Unity3D can benefit from UnityGeoAR's handling of Unity-
300 specific visualization tasks, as well as take advantage of an extensive range

301 of learning material for Unity3D¹⁰ to familiarize themselves with the Unity
302 environment if needed.

303 *4.2. Extensibility*

304 UnityGeoAR is highly extensible: On the one hand it is open-source and
305 depends almost exclusively on other open-source tools. On the other its ser-
306 vices are generally self-contained, and as such it is possible (and encouraged)
307 for developers to extend and adapt them as they see fit, by e.g. using dif-
308 ferent services for routing, geocoding, and elevation, or providing their own
309 reprojection implementations. Additionally, while UnityGeoAR does not of-
310 fer visualization methods, the Unity ecosystem provides access to a wealth
311 of assets such as 3D models, materials, textures, shaders, animations, etc, al-
312 lowing developers to build highly detailed, accurate geospatial visualizations.

313 *4.3. Fields of application*

314 Finally, a major impact of UnityGeoAR is identified in its potential for ap-
315 plication in multiple fields. Since it was originally developed as part of an
316 AR navigation app, we expect it to contribute in that field first and fore-
317 most, as it is an active research field as identified previously[6]. We identify
318 three active research avenues within AR navigation that UnityGeoAR can
319 contribute to: AR usability studies [7, 8, 3, 9], evaluation of visualization
320 techniques (e.g. symbology, level-of-detail) [10, 11, 12], and navigation tool
321 comparative studies in various environments [13, 14, 15, 16].

322 Furthermore, we anticipate that UnityGeoAR can provide benefits to other
323 fields implementing geospatial AR tools, such as cultural heritage for in-
324 situ reconstructions of historic sites [17, 18, 19] or tourist applications [20].

¹⁰<https://unity.com/learn>

325 Finally, due to UnityGeoAR's integration in the Unity3D engine we expect
326 it to be of use in interactive learning tools, serious games, and the gaming
327 sector in general.

328 **5. Conclusions**

329 In this article we have identified a common task in geo-located AR appli-
330 cations and highlighted its implementation complexities in aligning virtual
331 views with geo-located views in the real world. In response we have pre-
332 sented UnityGeoAR, a tool for Unity3D that combines multiple processes for
333 handling geo-AR tasks and provides a minimal API, offering an option to in-
334 dividual teams and researchers to avoid re-implementing common processes.
335 UnityGeoAR is still at an early development stage, and as such it still has
336 some limitations: It relies exclusively on a mobile device's embedded sensors,
337 and therefore will replicate any accumulating drift errors. Future develop-
338 ment will focus on the implementation of drift detection algorithms, both
339 for angular/compass drift and positional drift, so that UnityGeoAR can au-
340 tomatically detect whether the current virtual view is misaligned beyond a
341 certain threshold to the actual view. Furthermore, we plan to implement
342 drift correction algorithms so that UnityGeoAR can automatically and con-
343 tinuously correct such drift errors.

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